

Figure Z5

Figure Z5: Sub-clustering of cell types across tissues. (A-K) Cell subtypes or states of B-cell (A), macrophage (B), T-cell (C), dendritic cell (D), monocyte (E), tenocyte (F), smooth muscle cell (G), endothelial cell (H), glial cell (I), adipose stem cell (J), and fibro-adipogenic progenitor (K).